

Pooled Data stored and shared: Transfer final processed data for long-term use.

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1.3	31-03-2025	▪ Adapted based on comments and ready to be uploaded
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D10.6: Transfer final processed data for long-term use

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1. Executive summary

This deliverable (D10.6) describes the final transfer of processed data for long-term use including the Equal-Life website ([Studying the exposome for a healthier future for all children | Equal Life](#)), Equal-Life toolbox and guidebook, aggregate statistics, meta-data, anonymized enriched data, codes, pooled results, models for data mining, patent fillings etc.

A detailed description of the different products of the Equal-Life project was provided in D10.5 and Annex 3 in this document. These products will be accessible in different channels, including an open access website with no restrictions (<https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/>). Deliverable 10.6 is part of Task10.3. Data management, led by RIVM and co-led by INCHES and QUANTIA. This task focuses on the management of project data including raw data and the derived and processed final data. During the project, the research data were stored centrally at a server at RIVM for processing and midterm storage. Along ethical guidelines, the original data stay with the owners and will only be pooled at result level. This implies that matching of the exposure data to the (mental health and cognitive) outcome data also happens per cohort/data set. The pooled data were stored at the RIVM platform (Viadesk) for further statistical analysis in the different work packages. The data collected in the in-depth studies were dealt with by the respective owners of the cohorts. The new data collected from school-children are managed by the institute performing the measures and under their national regulations. The data and daily modifications during data processing are backed up daily to network drives. This data repository was used also for sharing with the partners in the consortium. In close collaboration with the partners dealing with communication, dissemination, and tool development this task planned and implemented the sharing of novel data and results created in the project. This also includes planning and implementing the toolbox and guidance document. After the project is finished the exposure data and the pooled results are incorporated in the Equal-Life toolbox. Deliverable 10.5 (confidential) describes the ways in which data is made accessible internally and externally also after the lifetime of the project. Here a summary is presented.

All data will be archived on Viadesk by RIVM as well as the AS, the pooled results and anonymised exposure data of those cohorts that allow the data to be made public in Zenodo, an EU repository.

A link (https://zenodo.org/communities/equal_life)

will be provided on the Equal-Life website <https://www.rivm.nl/en/international-projects/equal-life> and in the Equal-life tools and Guidebook which is externally hosted at (<https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/>). Specifically, the toolbox was developed using the Wix platform, which also provides hosting services. During the platform selection process, we ensured that Wix complies with all relevant European regulations (e.g., GDPR). The toolbox will be hosted also after the project by contract until May 2026. For the period after this additional funding will have to be sought (see also D10.5 and D10.7). An overview of the Equal-Life products in the Equal-Life toolbox is provided in Annex 3.

2. Data Summary

2.1. Existing data: eleven cohorts (birth cohorts and school studies).

The names of these cohorts and contact details and other characteristics are listed in Annex 1

Equal-Life uses primarily existing data derived from nine cohorts, and three longitudinal and cross-sectional studies in schoolchildren (N= > 250.000 pp) in nine EU member states. The data contain information from children (prenatal up to age 21) and their parents. The existing data was enriched with data related to the external exposome (physical and social) and intermediate effect markers (internal exposome once linked to exposures),

2.2 Six in-depth studies.

In addition, data has been collected from schoolchildren activities (in Sweden, Belgium, Germany, and the Netherlands) to study the distinct mechanisms underlying the association of environmental exposures with mental health and cognitive development indicators, including physical as well as social aspects (stress/restoration, sleep, supportive environments for children coping and self-regulation). In a sample of schoolchildren, activity patterns in for their age relevant settings were studied. Also, data were collected about time activity patterns in children and adolescents (in the Netherlands) and during experiments on children's auditory cognition (in Aachen, Germany).

Note (Annex 2) that Sleep study (Alpine 8-14 years) has been replaced by Sleep study (Alpine 11-14 years). The reasons for that change are also described in the updated Annex 1 of the GA part B and have been approved by the EC via an amendment.

Table 1: Overview of in-depth studies

Data collection studies	Responsible partner
Time activity exposure pattern study	TU/e
Auditory cognition in activity-based acoustic settings	RWTH
Preschool study Germany	TUK/ZEUS
Preschool study Belgium	UGhent
Sleep study on subsample of Alpine cohort cancelled	GUT
Secondary analyses on subsample of Alpine cohort (11-14 years)	GUT
Sleep study on subsample of stars cohort (17-19 years)	UGOT

GDPR does not allow for making the data from the in-depth study public. They can be shared with researcher if the aims align with the informed consent of participants (see D12.6) and with agreements of the PI's (see contact list in Annex 4).

2.3 Enriched and validated data

In the first phase of the project the XY coordinates were delivered by the data-owners to the data enrichers. Also, the bio-samples were selected and transferred to the laboratory performing the experiments. Data validation happened at both sides an iterative process meaning the provider and receiver side. This process is now finished. Important features are that the enrichment takes place per data set and that the data set, once completed, will not be stored except at the owner's side. In other words, the data owners do not see or share each other's (enriched) data. Among the enrichers themselves models might be exchanged as well as the underlying data, but this is highly dependent on the variables at hand. Providing enriched data minus the xy coordinates and pseudonymized by dummy addresses will be shared in Zenodo.

Providing IDs and XY coordinates by 9 data owners to the 6 data enrichers. (Done)

Providing IDs age and gender to 1 data enricher; (Done)

Enriching the XY coordinates with exposure data by 6 enrichers; (Done)

Enriching the IDs of selected children with biomarkers by 1 enricher. (Done)

Table 2: Overview of the status of the Data Transfer Agreements on 27-06-2024

Status Data Transfer Equal-Life based on information Viadesk, 27 June 2024

Group # Viadesk	Dataset	Data available on Viadesk (No / Yes)	Data provider	Data receivers						
				John Gulliver (ULEIC)	Gabriele Bolte (UB)	Alessandra Bozzon (TUD)	Maarten Hornikx (TUE)	Dick Botteldoorn (Ugent)	Maria Foraster (ISGlobal)	Katja Kanninen (UEF)
1	ABCD	Data available	Tanja Vrijkotte (AMC)							
2	ALSPAC	No data available	Charlotte Clark (ARUP)							
3	PIAMA	Data available	Jolanda Boer (RIVM)							
4a	RANCH-NL	Data available	Elise van Kempen (RIVM)							
5	NORAH	Data available	Maria Klatter (TUK)							
6	Alpine	Data available	Peter Lercher (GUT)							
7	STARS	Data available	Yun Chen (UGOT)							
8	BREATHE and WALNUTS	Data available	Maria Foraster (ISGlobal)							
9	FAIR	Data available	Jenny Selander (KI)							
10	FinnTwin12	Data available	Jaakko Kaprio (UH)							
11	Data transfer ISG-UE	Data available	Maria Foraster (ISGlobal)							

As shown in table 2, the exchange of XY coordinates is now finalized. This data was needed for the data owners and enrichers and no central storage was needed. This implies that there has been only

an exchange of data and once this process of exchange was finished the files at the exchange node of the RIVM was removed. It was checked whether the size of the enriched data sets causes issues, estimated to be over a million records (lines), including dummy coordinates, and some 500 columns at max.

For validation of the data we do not need a specified functionality. This task is the call of the enrichers before they share the data again and of the cohort owners (when receiving the enriched data set). Analysis by the enrichers will happen with their own tools, models etc.

Special attention is needed for **version management** on the datafiles; possibly more than one iteration is needed to optimise the enrichment. And also the process of validation can lead to multiple versions of the datafiles. It was recommended to centralise decision making about this. Also, it should be decided how the communication about these different versions is organized and what platform is suitable for this (NB Viadesk does not facilitate such interaction, but version control is well established).

Exchange of data on the built environment (D5.7 & D5.8) and natural environment (MS8) and environmental quality (D3.3) is finished.

Actions performed

1. Test the maximum size of exchange data sets
 - Checked if Viadesk and MS Teams provide the functionality needed (done)
 - Arranged for access right in the files. (done)
 - Save formats (CSV and GeoJSON). done
2. Exchange of models and data between enrichers.

Some enrichers shared model codes of transport models and underlying data. The best solution for internal collaboration in relation to a model code is GitHub. They (will) also provide code of the exposure metrics developed for data enrichment, so it is not only about (transport) models. Also there is a wish to exchange the underlying (traffic) data such as traffic volumes, number of trains (day, night), distance to green area, mean area of green/blue space). These will be geospatial data that can, indeed, be projected on a map, but most of them will be data attributes in tabular format (with attached geo-location per data record (attributes to these maps are simple tables containing for example height of buildings or traffic counts on streets). It was confirmed that all partners can work with GIT and exchanges can be performed in CSV files.

An overview of the data is provided in Annex 3, whereby a distinction is made between METADATA, DATA and CODES.

3. Transferring data for long term use

The Equal-Life toolbox and guidebook, metadata, publications, pooled results and codes are made available in two platforms: the website (<https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/>) and the EU repository Zenodo ([https://zenodo.org/communities/equal life](https://zenodo.org/communities/equal%20life)). A description is provided in the next paragraphs.

3.1 Wix

Wix.com is a cloud-based web development platform that allows users to create and manage professional websites. The platform provides an intuitive drag-and-drop editor, a vast library of customizable templates, and a suite of built-in tools that facilitate seamless collaboration. Wix enables co-design and co-creation with users by allowing multiple contributors to work on a website simultaneously, offering role-based access controls, and integrating real-time feedback mechanisms. These features make it a valuable solution for individuals, small businesses, and organizations looking to build and refine their online presence efficiently.

Wix's European headquarters is located in Dublin, Ireland, where it provides regional support and ensures adherence to European regulations. By maintaining a strong presence in Europe, Wix continues to enhance its services while aligning with the latest legal and regulatory requirements concerning data privacy, cybersecurity, and digital commerce.

Wix places a strong emphasis on data security and privacy and operates in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The platform provides website owners with dedicated tools to manage user consent, control personal data, and generate GDPR-compliant privacy policies. Users have the ability to access, modify, or delete their personal data, ensuring transparency and adherence to European data protection standards.

To ensure high performance, reliability, and security, Wix stores and processes data for European users within EU-based data centers, reinforcing its commitment to GDPR compliance and minimizing data transfers outside the European Economic Area (EEA).

3.2 Zenodo

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) is an EU Open Research Repository and is a Zenodo-community dedicated to fostering open science and enhancing the visibility and accessibility of research outputs funded by the European Union. The community is managed by European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) on behalf of the European Commission.

The mission of the repository is to support the implementation of the EU's open science policy, providing a trusted and comprehensive space for researchers to share their research outputs such as data, software, reports, presentations, posters and more. The EU Open Research Repository simplifies the process of complying with open science requirements, ensuring that research outputs from Horizon Europe, Euratom, and earlier Framework Programs are freely accessible, thereby accelerating scientific discovery and innovation.

The EU Open Research Repository serves as a complementary platform to the Open Research Europe (ORE) publishing platform. Open Research Europe focuses on providing a publishing venue for peer-reviewed articles, ensuring that research meets rigorous academic standards. The EU Open Research Repository provides a space for all the other research outputs including data sets, software, posters, and presentations that are out of scope for ORE. This holistic approach enables researchers to not only publish their findings but also share the underlying data and materials that support their work, fostering transparency and reproducibility in the scientific process.

The EU Open Research Repository is funded by the European Union under grant agreement no. 101122956(HORIZON-ZEN). For more information about the project see <https://about.zenodo.org/projects/horizon-zen/>. Zenodo is funded by the European Commission.

We selected Zenodo as the primary repository for long-term archiving, as it offers a trusted, sustainable, and secure solution for preserving outputs beyond the lifetime of the project. While GitHub remains the preferred platform for active development and collaboration during the project, Zenodo provides a more robust option for permanent storage. Nonetheless, the GitHub repository will remain accessible for several years after the project's completion to ensure continuity and ease of access.

Zenodo addresses the need for long-term preservation by creating a permanent archive linked to GitHub, ensuring that key outputs remain available and citable over time. Below is a summary of key differences:

- **Archival Permanence:** Zenodo is specifically designed for long-term preservation, retaining archived items for the lifetime of CERN (minimum 20 years). Each release is stored as a tarball, assigned a DOI (Digital Object Identifier), and made independent from GitHub, ensuring it remains unchanged over time.
- **Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs):** Zenodo automatically assigns DOIs to each archived release, facilitating academic citation and improving discoverability.
- **Integration with GitHub:** Zenodo offers seamless integration with GitHub, automatically archiving each release and generating a new DOI, thus simplifying the process of creating a citable, permanent version of the software or dataset.

By combining GitHub for ongoing development and Zenodo for final archival, we ensure both usability during the project and preservation beyond its duration.

4. Implementation and maintenance

An account has been opened at Zenodo and the data and codes will be submitted stepwise before the end of the project in June 2025 but preferably at an earlier stage. Maintenance is guaranteed until the existence of CERN. The potential risk is that if the data will be deposited in June there is not much margin to create the link between Zenodo and the Equal-Life toolbox. Therefore the process will have to speed up as much as possible and the coordinating institute will take on board the task of maintenance of the toolbox with additional funding.

5. Other issues

n.a.

6. References

1. [About | Zenodo](#)
2. [Zenodo - Wikipedia](#)
3. [Wix.com - Wikipedia](#)

Glossary

Aggregate Statistics (AS)	When data are aggregated, groups of observations are replaced with summary statistics based on those observations.
Biomarkers	a measurable indicator of some biological state or condition.
Exposome	a measure of all the exposures of an individual in a lifetime and how those exposures relate to health.
Intermediate effect marker	a measurable indicator of a biological state indicative of future effects
Internal exposome	A biological response to cumulative exposures.
Pooled analyses	statistical technique for combining the results of multiple epidemiological studies.
Pooled data	Combined data or combined information rather than the raw data.
Pooled Result (PR)	Pooled Results
ExCo	Executive Committee
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GIS	Geographical Information Systems
IFC	Informed Consent
IoT	Internet of Things
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
OSM	OpenStreetMap
POPD	Protection of Personal Data;

Annex 1:

Data type, design, country, geographical area age size, years, number of children, coordinates available

Cohort name	Cohort type	Study design	Country and geographical scale	Geographical area	Age range (years)	Calendar years	Number of children	Geo-coordinates available
ABCD	Birth	Longitudinal	Netherlands (regional)	Netherlands	Prenatal-14	2003-2018	8,266	yes
ALPINE	Birth (Retrospective)	Cross-sectional	Austria, Italy (regional)	Inntal, Wipptal Nord (Austria) and Wipptal Süd (Italy)	(prenatal) 8-11	2004-2005	1,251	yes
ALSPAC	Birth	Longitudinal	U.K. (regional)	Bristol, Old County	Prenatal-11	1991-2008	14,541	no
BREATHE	Child, school	Longitudinal	Spain (regional)	Barcelona, St. Cugat	7-11	2012-2013	2,878	yes
FAIR	Birth	Longitudinal	Sweden (regional)	Stockholm, Gothenburg, Malmö	Prenatal-12	2007-2018	200,000	yes
FinnTwin12	Twin-family	Longitudinal	Finland (national)	Finland	11-24	1994-2006	5,600	yes
NORAH	Child, school	Cross-sectional	Germany (national)	Germany	8	2012	1,243	yes
PIAMA	Birth	Longitudinal	Netherlands (national)	Netherlands	Prenatal-20	1997-2018	4,000	yes
RANCH	Child, school	Cross-sectional	Netherlands (regional)	Amsterdam & Schiphol	9-10	2002	737	yes
STARS	Adolescence	Cross-sectional	Sweden (regional)	Gothenburg, Västra Götaland	13	2015-2019	2,283	no
WALNUTS	Child/adolescence, school	Cross-sectional	Spain (regional)	Barcelona	11-14	2016-2018	700	yes

Annex 2: Overview of in-depth studies (type, scale, country, age, nr of children, WP, criteria method).

Sub study	Study Type	Scale	Country	Ages	Year	Nr of children	Used in	Exclusion Criteria	Method
Time activity exposure pattern study	Cross sectional of children aged 0-21	National	NL	0-3, 4-7, 8-12, 13-17, 18-21	2022	2031	WP4	Lack of consent by either parent or child	GPS measurements combined with activity diary and questionnaires on demographic information and health (self-rated mental health and SDQ)
Auditory cognition in activity-based acoustic settings	Series of cross-sectional studies of children vs. young adults	Aachen	DE	3-10 years (children) vs. >18 years (adults)	2022 - 2024	8 to 10 * (30 children + 24 adults)	WP3	Normal hearing abilities, German speaking, healthy (no obvious behavioural syndromes), lack of participant's consent	Child-appropriate listening experiments (adapted step by step after each experiment) to assess auditory cognition in children compared to adults in different activity-based acoustic settings incl. noise
Preschool study	14 months longitudinal study t1: preschool t2: end of grade 1	Regional	Germany Belgium	5-7	2022-2024	50 per site	WP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient proficiency in the language of instruction Diagnosis of developmental disorder Intake of central nervous system medication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental exposure assessment (at home, at school) via modelling, sensors, questionnaires, enrichment Social exposures (questionnaires) Cognitive Test Battery School achievement (t2, questionnaire) Mental health and well-being (Questionnaires) EEG Parameters of Speech Perception and gating Activity Patterns (questionnaires) Perceived environmental quality
Sleep (Alpine) cancelled	Subsample based on age	Region	Austria	8-10 8-14	2022	25/100-200	WP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sleep apnea , BMI>30 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physiological measures of sleep using portable recording of ECG and 3 direction movements
Sleep (Alpine)	Subsample based on age	Region	Austria	11-14	2022	156/30 (nested)	WP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sleep apnea , BMI>30 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secondary analysis

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Sleep (stars)	Subsample based on age	Gothenburg	Sweden	17-19	2022	100-200	Wp1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Sleep apnea, severe asthma, snoring, known allergic skin reaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Physiological measures of sleep using portable recording of ECG• Noise exposure (indoor/outdoor)
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Annex 3 Overview of the products in the Equal-Life toolbox

Type of product	WP/PI	comments	Location/re-requirements	Institute
I. META-DATA				
Equal-Life GUIDEBOOK	WP8/WP9 ZEUS		Open website , no restriction for access to cohort information-- Find function is included on the website	ZEUS Quantia
Overview of publications and public deliverables	WP10/all		Open website	RIVM
- Overview of all (meta) data available in the toolbox (fiches)	WP3/WP9/WP10		Open website	St George University, QUANTIA RIVM
- Overview of all cohorts and school studies	WP7		Open website	Karolinska Institute
- Overview of harmonized data and variables in each cohort	WP7		EHEN catalogue/Molgenis	Karolinska Institute QUANTIA
-Overview of socially and equity-relevant community-level indicators	WP4		Open website	University Bremen
-Overview of physical exposome data (indoor, outdoor, built, natural, lifestyle)	WP3 ULEIC, ISGlobal/GHENT, Tue/ WP5		Open website	ISGlobal St George University Technical University Eindhoven University Ghent Technical University Delft
- Guidance to retrieve exposure data for specific locations	WP3, WP4, WP5		Open website	St George University University Bremen Technical University Delft
-New exposure data or models to obtain these derived in WP 3, 4 and 5	WP3, WP5		Open website	St George University University Bremen Technical University Delfts
- Overview of interventions	WP7, WP8, WP9		Open website	Karolinska Institute RIVM

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- Case studies of equity impact assessment of urban interventions /Good practice	WP4 (WP7)		Open website	University Bremen Karolinska Institute
- Conceptual models on mechanisms... (WP 1) and on the Social Exposome (WP4)	WP1/WP4		Open website	Gothenburg University University Bremen
- Framework to consider equity aspects in urban interventions	WP4		Open website	University Bremen
II DATA				
-Enriched data without the xy coordinates Including fake addresses	WP3, WP5	Access can only be given with consent of the data owners	Zenodo	Cohort owners See table 5*
Aggregate statistics	WP6/WP7	- Access to AS can only be given with consent of the data owner within the consortium as well as outside the consortium	Zenodo	Cohort owners see table 5*
Pooled results	WP6/WP7	Access to pooled results only with consent of all data owners of data included in the pooled results	Zenodo	RIVM

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-Linkage between biomarkers and exposures (internal exposome).	WP2, and cohort owners	Biomarker determinants will be managed and shared by the responsible institutes and under their national regulations	Sharing with others is limited FinnTwin12 data findable in https://thl.fi/en/research-and-development/thl-biobank/for-researchers	UEF IISPV Helsinki University
III CODES				
Codes enabling pooled data analyses	WP6 (in collaboration with WP7)		Zenodo	RIVM
-Codes enabling data enrichment See also above -New exposure data or models to obtain these derived in WP 3, 4 and 5	WP3, WP4, WP5		Zenodo	ISGlobal St George University Technical university Eindhoven University Ghent Technical University Delft Bremen University

Annex 4: Contact details per institute

List of Beneficiaries				
No	Name	Short name	Country	Contact details
1	RIJKSINSTITUUT VOOR VOLKSGEZONDHEID EN MILIEU	RIVM	Netherlands	Elise.van.kempen@rivm.nl
2	GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET	UGOT	Sweden	YunChen <Yun.Chen@wlab.gu.se>
3	ITA-SUOMEN YLIOPISTO	UEF	Finland	Katja Kanninen <katja.kanninen@uef.fi>
4	UNIVERSITY OF LEICESTER	ULEIC	United Kingdom	Anna Hansell <ah618@leicester.ac.uk>
5	UNIVERSITAET BREMEN	UB	Germany	Gabriele Bolte <gbolte@uni-bremen.de>
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15	ZEUS GMBH, ZENTRUM FUR ANGEWANDTE PSYCHOLOGIE, UMWELT- UND SOZIALFORSCHUNG	ZEUS	Germany	Dirk Schreckenber (ZEUS) <schreckenber@zeusgmbh.de>
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23	ST GEORGE'S HOSPITAL MEDICAL SCHOOL	SGUL	United Kingdom	John Gulliver <jgulliver@sgul.ac.uk>